

Challenges of developing Academic writing for Saudi students studying in the United Kingdom

Umair Siddiqui

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Abstract

This study investigated the Challenges of developing Academic writing for Saudi students studying in the United Kingdom. The study took place in the Preston English Academy based in the city of Preston in the United Kingdom. This research was conducted using the Qualitative approach. Approximately 10 Saudi students and 4 English teachers were involved in this study. The focus of this investigation was to answer the three research questions associated with this study. A questionnaire was used to collect information from both Saudi students and their teachers in this English Academy.

The findings of this study found that due to various factors such as previous and current learning experiences, economic conditions and L1 interference caused by the differences between the Arabic and English language exacerbates the situation faced by Saudi students studying in the UK. Students therefore had low motivation and engagement levels in class which in turn affected the development of academic writing skills further. It is hoped that the insight gained from this study can benefit future and current Saudi students and their teachers both in the United Kingdom and various English universities throughout the world as well as Saudi Arabian educators.

Introduction

The aim of this study is to identify the difficulties of developing academic writing faced by Saudi students studying in the UK. Academic writing is a challenging skill to teach Saudi students due to a mixture of linguistic and cultural differences between the English and Arabic language. This study is focusing on the Academic Writing difficulties of Saudi students however it is a similar challenge for other second language students from Arabic speaking countries as well as a lot of global students when they arrive to study at UK universities.

English is an important lingua franca as the language is used in Business and global communications which has led to demand for students from different language backgrounds to study at prestigious universities in the U.S.A and the United Kingdom. Students from non-English speaking countries are increasingly seeking to study in the UK especially in the UK over the previous decade (Espinoza 2017) while such articles show an increasing amount of foreign students studying in UK universities it fails to take into account the struggle international students and in particular Saudi students face when it comes to adapting to UK universities as students are exposed to a new culture and students negotiate and come to terms to the new educational system in the UK with academic writing practices coming as a shock to most Saudi students.

Aim of the study

This study aims to answer the following questions:

- 1.What challenges, in terms of developing academic writing, do Saudi students face whilst studying in the UK?**
- 2.Does L1 interference contribute to academic writing difficulties for Saudi students?**
- 3.How can Saudi students be helped to face the challenges of academic writing?**

A review conducted on the literature failed to find any previous studies which is specifically related to the academic writing difficulties experienced by Saudi students in the United Kingdom.

The purpose of the study is to be able to understand what are the difficulties faced by Saudi students in terms of Academic writing as well as understanding the relationship between Arabic as an L1 and English as an L2 and as to how L1 interference can lead to difficulties in English academic writing. The first two questions are critical as it directly help to answer the third question which is as to how a solution can be formed to tackle the challenges of Academic writing so that corrective measures can be put in place to help address the difficulties experienced by Saudi students in the UK when it comes to academic writing.

Literature Review

Characteristics of Academic writing

According to Strongman (2014) “Academic writing is about choosing words carefully to communicate complex ideas to a range of readers and audiences” Students have to be able to communicate complex ideas which needs a good knowledge of academic discourse in order to effectively communicate complex ideas in Academic writing.

Academic writing can be defined as scholarly writing where it is profoundly different from writing about personal experience instead academic writing is dependent on evidences from academic readings (Sibiya 2010) Therefore academic writing cannot be subjective and must maintain an objective observational edge as each statement made by the reader must be backed up using academic evidences.

Hyland (2002) “Academic writing is not just about conveying an ideational ‘content’, it is also about the representation of self. Recent research has suggested that academic prose is not completely impersonal, but that writers gain credibility by projecting an identity invested with individual authority” (1091) As Hyland states that academic writing must be backed up by using logical evidences with the use of third person pronoun being recommended.

Academic writing is a prerequisite for students studying at higher education institutes in the UK. This specific genre of writing is based on writing about a given subject using a formal register of the English language. It requires the writer to be objective using evidences and critical thinking to support any ideas being written by the writer on the given subject matter. The intended target of such academic writing are teachers and academics of the given field.

According to Irvin (2010) Academic writing involves using the critical thinking approach to “evaluation that asks you to demonstrate knowledge and show proficiency” (pg.8) with a major emphasis on being able to discern and critically analyse every statement without taking it in as pure facts is a sign of critical thinking. This is one of the main weaknesses found in many NS and NNEs at the university level with a lot of marks being lost in academic writing due to a shortage of this skill. This can be blamed on previous education experience as academic writing is less prevalent in many foreign countries where there is less emphasis on academic writing due to the difference in the local education system.

According to a study conducted by Hale et al. (1996) a study was conducted in universities in the USA. The study discovered that the most popular written forms of academic genres at universities are documented essays, summarization, book reviews and research proposals. The study also discovered that depending on the subjects taken at universities such as social sciences and humanities which required length academic research essays. Hale et al. (1996) continues that these academic essays require students to write argumentative and exposition type of texts with a problem and resolution approach. Comparing whilst analysing texts with a critical thinking approach is required at most US and UK universities (Hale et al. 1996). T

Swales (2001:52) states that academic writing at universities ‘is no longer a straightforward cumulative process, but more of a matter of new starts and unexpected adjustments.’ This shows that Academic writing isn’t about the quantity of work but that it points towards a

critical thought process where the student must adapt and develop his or her argument or analysis in order to reach an appropriate resolution in their academic writing discourse.

According to Starfield (2001) It is not a simple process for students to just learn language according to the degree they are studying for but in fact it is very intricate and necessitates a profounder understanding of the production of the texts, and the context in which the writing was produced in so that it can be evaluated appropriately (Johns, 1997) In the case of this study Academic writing requires not only the understanding of Academic English lexis but it also requires how to produce Academic texts alongside the context which is in accordance to the Academic research environment so that it can be evaluated correctly this can be linked to the RQ as it is a process of developing Academic writing.

Swales (2001:52) goes on to state that Academic writing ‘is no longer a cumulative process, but more a matter of new starts and unexpected adjustments.’ This states that it is not about just collecting data and producing a lengthy piece of writing but ‘unexpected adjustments’ shows that the writer has to critically assess the information they are collecting which can be done when there is a deeper understanding of the roles played by the authors of the texts, and the contexts and circumstances in which these academic texts were produced in (Johns 1997). This shows that context and evaluations is an essential part of Academic writing.

According to Ballard and Clanchy (1997) Context in Academic writing is a major point of difficulty for most students as they struggle to produce their academic writing in an acceptable form. NNES will struggle more than NES due to the lack of understanding of the conventions and requirements of academic writing at English Universities. As the study mentioned the difficulty of NNES adapting to the conventions and requirements of Academic writing at English universities it will be worthwhile to investigate how this affects this study’s RQs as the challenges of developing academic writing can be pinpointed to the difficulty in adapting to the new Academic conventions being experienced by NNES which can also relate to Saudi students in the UK which will help to identify the challenges of academic writing and a potential solution for Saudi students in the UK.

Dong (1997:10) maintains that the premise of academic writing is based on students learning each disciplines specific academic rules and how to apply them as different degrees at university require different rules of academic discourse when it comes to writing. Dong (1997) argues that NNES struggle with academic writing due to the difference in Academic writing requirements in their home countries and how they have been trained. This point raised by Dong requires further study as this can answer this study’s RQs as the difficulties of Academic writing experienced by NNES and specifically Saudi students may possibly originate from the way they have been taught in Saud Arabia before arriving to the UK.

Many NNS studying in graduate and post graduate courses in Western Universities despite years of prior ESL (English as a Second Language) tutoring “often fail to recognise and appropriately use the conventions and features of academic prose.” (Hinkel, 2003: 4)(Johnson, 1997) Despite the NNS best efforts they most commonly presented academic writing which amounted to being “vague and confusing, rhetorically unstructured and overtly personal” (Hinkel, 2003: 4)(Johnson, 1997)

Academic writing requires the correct format and academic lexis which fits in well with the subject in hand in an objective manner (Turner 2011) This requirement of the use of correct register fits in well with the requirement of Academic writing as the appropriate lexis must be used to ensure an objective approach to academic writing.

A study conducted in Universities in the USA by Murshidi (2014) found that “less than 31% of Emirati and Saudi students feel ‘comfortable’ in completing written assignments.”(P 87) furthermore Murshidi (2014) found that Saud students struggled with “grammar, word choice and sentence construction”(P87) With Saudi students in the USA struggling it further enhances the need for a similar study to be conducted in the UK in relation to the RQ’s of this study as to what is contributing to Saudi student’s academic writing difficulties in the UK and as to what part of Academic writing that the student’s struggle with so that this study can identify the root cause and suggest possible solutions to help improve the predicament Saudi students have with Academic writing in the UK.

Language challenge

Arabic is the official language of Saudi Arabia and is the mother tongue (L1) of Saudi students studying in the UK. There is a fundamental difference between English and Arabic with various structural differences. For example the Arabic alphabet is different from the Latin alphabets used by English, Spanish and Italian etc. with Arabic alphabets being completely different in structure and phonetic sounds. (Al-Sughaiyer 2004)

According to Shabbir and Bughio (2009) Arabic and English have many structural differences “Arabic language has no capitalization and its punctuation conventions are different from the English language” (P.76) This therefore indicates that Saudi learners will struggle to learn English rules specific to writing due to fundamental differences between Arabic and English.

Social integration

In contrast to NS that have the social support of being able to study in their home country with their family and friends living close by NNES struggle with adjusting to living in the UK with coming to terms to the new environment and culture compared to their country back home. “Only a small percentage of International students reported having close friendships with domestic students...The findings also indicated that the more interaction international students had with Americans, the greater their adjustment” (Andrade 2006: 136) (Hechanova-Alampay 2002) This is very useful for this study’s RQ as to how the social factor affects Saudi students and their ability to learn academic writing. If the study finds that Saudi students are indeed socializing and meeting their own nationals and avoiding mixing in with other nationalities or classroom students then it would be an important factor in the study which would signify that the less they interact with the local population and other students the more they will struggle with adjusting to the social environment they find themselves in which can be detrimental to their motivation and engagement in the Academic English classroom.

International students studying in the UK

In today’s globalised world English has taken it’s place as an official global lingua franca as the financial and business world is using English as a Global lingua franca to communicate all across the world (Seidlhofer, 2005). The UK alongside the United States of America has a historical place in the globalised world as a prestigious country to attain higher education from (Harris and McNamara, 2002) due to the higher economic benefits of having a UK University qualification with the prospects of being able to apply for higher paying jobs in the oversea

student's home countries (Bodycott, 2009). Economic realities have also contributed towards the increasing trends of overseas students wishing to study in the UK due to the recent Brexit causing the British pound to fall which has made the prospect of studying at UK universities even more appealing due to the cheaper currency exchange with the UK (Warrel, 2017). The importance of English as a Lingua franca in the globalised world has led to an increase of students from non-English speaking countries to study in countries such as the UK and USA (Turner, 2011).

All the above factors have led to an increase in Saudi students enrolling to UK universities as a result demand for Foundation English courses have increased due to the increased influx of foreign students. Academic pressures of adjusting to the new educational system foreign students encounter in the UK coupled with adjusting to new social realities can cause social anxiety as students struggle to communicate with fellow students as well as struggling with understanding their course material and working on their academic writing which is needed for producing academic writing assignments (Goodfellow, 2004).

Being able to fit in socially and difficulty in language skills cause a major impediment to students trying to adjust to life in an English-speaking country (Andrade, 2006). Foreign students studying in UK universities face a lot of social challenges as being unable to communicate in English with the local students contributes to a difficult challenge of adjusting to living and studying in the UK or any English-speaking country (Andrade, 2006). According to this source in relation to my Research Question (RQ) Saudi students will also face this issue as adjusting to living life in the UK which is fundamentally different to the type of culture and lifestyle they are used to in their home country of Saudi Arabia. These two factors of Language and social skills are crucial factors when it comes to Saudi students adjusting to their new student lives in the UK as it is for other foreign students.

According to Lalasz, Doane, Springer, and Dahir (2014) Foreign students studying in English speaking countries that lack ability in English tend to underperform academically as they struggle to communicate effectively with their university teachers about the problems they are facing in their studies or lecture as a result this impedes these types of students from improving academically. According to Krashen (1982) The affective filter which is a 'negative emotional' reaction to a student's environment where anxiety and difficulties of acquiring language can effectively raise the 'affective filter' of a learner which impedes language acquisition. This can help with this study as the emotional state of a learner in relation to Krashen's (1982) affective filter theory can be taken into account when assessing why Saudi students struggle with academic writing in the UK. This can also be questioned as to its validity due to it being research conducted a long time ago back in 1982 however recent academic studies have maintained this as an essential theory in the classroom (Butzkamm and Caldwell, 2009)

Sawir (2005) stated that foreign students studying in a English speaking country such as Australia struggle with writing and speaking in English which has impeded their academic life in the classroom. Sawir stated that it is imperative that research is carried out to find out how a student's previous learning experiences in their countries of origins contribute to their difficulties in English. This paper will focus on this aspect to ascertain how the learning environment in Saudi Arabia contributes to Saudi Students difficulties in academic writing in the UK.

According to a study by Ramburuth (2001) An academic writing comparison was made between NNS (Non Native Students) and NES (native English students) at a department in an

Australian University with the findings reporting that 76 percent of NNES students required “intensive” writing training compared to just 20 percent of NES. The study is however ambiguous as it does not state what nationalities the NNES consisted of which necessitates the need for more research to be done on the Academic writing difficulties of this study on Saudi students studying in the UK. Andrade (2006) stated that students with a positive or negative previous learning experience can either help or hinder NNES as negative learning experiences in their home countries “provoked feelings of embarrassment, frustration, disappointment and boredom.” (Andrade 2006: 135) This is important for this study’s RQ as a further study on the previous learning experiences of Saudi students will contribute to the findings on this study.

Saudi Students

In recent years the UK has become an attractive destination for many Saudi students and tourists as demand for British visa’s carries on rising in Saudi Arabia (Muhammad, 2014) This shows that the UK remains a popular destination for Saudi students who are looking to complete their higher education in order to get well paid jobs back in Saudi Arabia.

Saudi Arabia is situated in Asia in the region known as the Middle East. The oil rich country has a native population of Arab people. The Arabic language dominates daily day to day life in Saudi Arabia as the official language in use in day to day life, Religion and government (Buchele 2008) Arabic is the official medium of instruction in the Saudi education system whereas English is taught to all Saudi students from Primary school and onwards with Arabic centred religious studies taking precedence. (Sedgwick 2001) As a result of Arabic being the medium of instruction in the Saudi curriculum English is seen as a secondary and ignored by Saudi students as they focus on Arabic in order to progress in their studies. The native language of Arabic is prevalent across the country with little to no opportunity of to speak in English except for communication with foreign workers and visitors to Saudi Arabia. Students are as a result fully fluent in speaking and writing Arabic however their English writing and speaking ability is negatively affected due to the lack of use. (Rahman and Al-Haisoni 2013)

There are also different views as to why NNES struggle with Academic writing with NNES and teachers having different opinions as a study by Robertson et al. (2000) found that “international students lacked critical thinking skills, had difficulty understanding spoken English and had weak writing skills whereas students criticized instructors of their use of colloquial English and rapid speech.”(Andrade 2006: 138)(Robertson et al. 2000). The study identifying student perception shows the need to research this further with Saudi students as to whether their academic difficulties is arising from not being able to understand their English teachers in the UK and will help to answer the RQ’s. Teachers can also give a more detailed picture as to why NNES struggle with academic writing as teachers stated in a study conducted by Robertson et al. (2000) that “international students do not take sufficient responsibility for their own learning.”(P100) This study cannot be taken as indicative to UK Saudi students as this study was conducted in Australia and did not solely involve Saudi students in Australia but it would help this study to enhance it’s finding if UK teachers teaching Saudi students can also be included in this study to try to acquire their point of view as to why Saudi students are struggling with Academic writing in the UK.

L1 Interference

The term L1 refers to a learner's first language or 'mother tongue' which plays a role in a learner's acquisition of L2 which is also known as the target language or second language of a learner. L1 interference takes place when students apply their knowledge of their L1 in the process of acquiring L2 (Weinreich 1953). The difficulty level of acquiring L2 depends on "the amount of effort required to learn an L2 pattern...on the extent to which the target language pattern was similar or different from a native language pattern." (Ellis 1994: 349). This is relevant to this study as the L1 of Saudi students is Arabic which is profoundly different from the English L2 which is being acquired by Saudi students studying in the UK. Ellis (1994) states that when L1 and L2 are profoundly different then negative transfer takes place. As the Arabic language is different in many ways from the English language. According to Lado's (1957) contrastive analysis hypothesis (CAH) is used in linguistics to compare two or more distinct languages so that variances and resemblances can be found between them. The theory claims that L2 acquisition errors made by learners can be identified by analysing the Phonology and syntactic topographies of both L1 and L2 with that being Arabic and English in this study so that potential L1 errors can be identified (Ellis 1994).

According to Lado (1957:p2) "...the student who comes in contact with a foreign language will find some features of it quite easy and others extremely difficult. Those elements that are similar to his mother tongue will be simple for him, and those elements that are different will be difficult." Arabic and English are completely different as English is based on Roman alphabets and Arabic is based on Arabic alphabets with learners from Spain and Italy finding it easier to learn English as an L2 due to sharing the same alphabets (Ellis 1994) whereas Arabic learners will find this more difficult compared to other European learners who share the same Roman alphabet and similarities between their mother tongue and English as an L2. As the exclusive forms between Arabic and English are numerous with different patterns in both languages both in the oral and written form the greater the difficulty in learning and L1 interference arises in acquiring the L2 (Weinreich 1953). Unfortunately there are major criticisms of this method with this specifically not working well with empirical forms of testing as many errors concentrate on purely the linguistic differences with the analysis neglecting to consider the psycholinguistic difficulties during L2 acquisition (Yi 2012). Therefore this study would be better advised to consider both the linguistic and psycholinguistic process of acquisition for Saudi students studying in the UK so that the RQ can be addressed in a sufficient manner.

Spelling errors

The English language is very inconsistent when it comes to the spelling of English words for example Knowledge contains the letter K which is silent when pronounced as "nowledge" however the addition of a silent k in knowledge causes issues for Arabic learners as the spelling of Arabic words corresponds with the pronunciation of various Arabic words such as قلب (heart) with the way it is spelt in Arabic corresponding with the pronunciation of the word. According to Morley (1991) The English language has an inherent weakness where there is an inconsistency when it comes to English spelling. Saudi learners would therefore struggle with various other words with inconsistencies such as Technology(tecknology), cat(Kat) and Second(Sekond) etc.

The transfer of L1 Arabic phonology

As Arabic is profoundly different phonetically compared to English this can cause negative L1 transfer (Weinreich 1953) As the Arabic alphabet contains 28 distinct alphabets with 25 being consonants and 3 consisting of long vowels with differences in pronunciation caused by the different lengths of short vowels which affects spelling when it comes to writing in Arabic (Abu-Rabia and Taha,2006) This can cause issues when it comes to English academic writing as the letter P in the English alphabet system does not exist in Arabic phonology (Ellis 1994) therefore errors are made when it comes to spelling English words such as Phone which is replaced by Bhone or Pepsi being written as Bepsi in English writing by Arabic learners. Saudi learners therefore struggle with differentiating between P and B when it comes to English writing and pronunciation. According to Fender (2008) Arabic learners are likely to struggle with the spelling of multi syllable words such as philosophy being spelt incorrectly by Arabic learners.

Saudi learners often struggle with English vowels as it contains more vowels than the Arabic language does therefore they struggle with what is termed as “vowel blindness” (Khan, 2013: p.26) therefore Saudi students forget to include vowels in their writing such “tble” instead of table. This can cause difficulties when trying to develop academic writing for Saudi students in the UK.

How to help Saudi students with challenges of academic writing?

The literature review in this study has identified three main factors when it comes to the major issues Saudi students experience when it comes to developing Academic writing with it being:

1. Linguistic differences between L1 and L2 (L1 interference)
2. Sociocultural challenges
3. Motivational challenge of learning English

We will address all the major challenges so that the literature review can identify research based on how to help Saudi students overcome these challenges whilst studying in the UK.

Linguistic differences between L1 and L2 (L1 interference)

Swan (1985) argues that a learners L1 can cause difficulties in acquiring L2 (English) however he also claims that’s direct translation can also be an easier teaching methodology rather than completely omitting the L1 from the English classroom. Unfortunately, the current popularity throughout the ESL world of teaching only using the L2 may have imperialistic and commercial overtones (Weschler, 1997).

Teachers must maintain English as the main language of instruction in the classroom however Willis (1981) states that “L1 may still be useful” (p.14) This shows that Saudi students arriving to study in the UK should not be excluded from being taught using their L1 especially for the students with a lower level of English. As using the L1 is very important especially at the lower levels of English classes (Cole, 1998). This saves valuable time and effort for teachers in classes as Saudi students from lower English levels would struggle to understand definitions and instructions in their new classrooms in the United Kingdom therefore a teacher should translate certain difficult definitions and instructions during the first few weeks of the Academic English preparation course before students develop further.

Therefore the use of L1 can be very beneficial in reducing L1 interference as students come to terms with the L2. However, this is only useful for lower level learners and not applicable to higher level English learners from Saudi Arabia. There is also a correct time and place for such L1 translations and must not be overemployed in a classroom to its detriment (Atkinson, 1993).

Sociocultural challenges

The study has identified that one of the major reasons for Saudi students struggling studying Academic writing in the UK is to do with the weaknesses of teaching English in Saudi Arabia with the Audio lingual method of teaching (Al Hazmi 2003) with the teacher reducing student speaking time and basing the lesson on talking throughout with students not getting the chance to ask or enquire about the lesson with the students resulting to being passive in class as the learning is teacher centred in Saudi classrooms (Al Kubaidi 2014) Therefore developing Academic English writing would require lessons to be taught in a more receptive way with the student centred approach (Jordan 1997). The methodology employed by Saudi teachers therefore hinders academic writing development as writing conventions that develop academic writing is not taught in the Saudi Curriculum (Al Haisoni 2012)

The study identified that there were issues with adjusting to the new realities of social integration when it comes to a new learning culture in Western universities with Liu (1999) recommending that NNS should receive greater attention to their learning needs compared to NS with the implementation of teaching assistants and the use of methods learnt in their previous learning experiences in their respective home countries such as Saudi Arabia in the study by Al Haisoni (2012). Due to this traditional approach of teaching English teachers in the UK will have to help Saudi students adjust to the different teaching methodology in the UK with a preferential adjustment factor taken into account to ensure Saudi students have a smooth transition and to remove the passive learning habits acquired in Saudi Arabia. The lack of confidence in Saudi students are apparent due to English being taught by NNE teachers in Saudi Arabia it is therefore apparent that Arabic is used in English classrooms to explain different grammar points with the Grammar translation method affecting the confidence of Saudi students as a result (El Khafaifi 2005). The lack of confidence can lead to a lack of confidence as the students are not able to confidently work hard to acquire academic English writing skills.

Motivational Challenges

Gardners and Lambert (1972, p.3) have argued that “the learner motivation to learn is thought to be determined by his attitudes towards the other group in particular and by his orientation towards the learning task itself”. This shows that there is a distinct relationship between the learner’s motivation and their attitude which leads to the amount of effort being put in will fluctuate depending on the student’s motivation to develop academic writing.

Motivation is an essential part of learning English as well as developing Academic English writing. It is

Al-Tamimi and Shuib (2009) argue that Saudi students have low motivation when it comes to learning English as Arabic is the dominant language in Saudi Arabia with English not having a use in Saudi Arabia. English has therefore been relegated to being seen as language needed to “pass” exams and seldom used in the average Saudi classroom (El Khafaifi 2005). This attitude is then carried over to the UK when Saudi students arrive to study in the UK. This study will need to investigate this further to find out if Saudi students have low motivation here in UK classrooms and how it affects their ability to develop academic writing.

Conclusion

In conclusion the literature review conducted links in well with the research questions based on what challenges learners face when studying academic writing in an English speaking country however the study has been unable to identify any relevant research done on the struggles of Saudi learners in UK Universities and therefore validates the need for further studies to be conducted into the factors that cause Academic writing difficulties for Saudi students as the literature review shows that the L1 interference alongside social and lifestyle changes alongside the previous ESL learning experiences of Saudi students in the Saudi Education system contributes to the current difficulties of Academic writing for Saudi Students. Therefore, the main premise of the study will focus on recommendations that would provide answers towards how academic writing can be improved for Saudi students studying in the UK.

Methodology

Introduction

As mentioned earlier, this study is exploring the challenges of developing academic writing for Saudi students studying in the United Kingdom. This chapter will elaborate on the methodology applied in the research process of this study. The participants will be made up of Saudi students enrolled in a private language academy and the teachers that are teaching these Saudi students within this private language academy. The data will be collected using questionnaires which will be available in two different versions one for teachers and one for Saudi students.

Research methodology

The study is based on the qualitative research method, which would identify what the challenges of developing English academic writing is for Saudi Arabian students in the United Kingdom. This study was initiated between two perspectives; The teachers that taught these Saudi Students in the UK and the Saudi students studying in the UK. Questionnaires and semi structured interviews were used to collect data from the Saudi students and their teachers. The questionnaires were used to collect informative data from both students and teachers so that it could provide an overview of the data collected. An interview was conducted from two perspectives with a teacher and a student so that the research questions of this study could be addressed in detail with the questionnaires giving a general demographic overview of the responses of the participants on the research questions of the study.

According to Gephart (2004) there are 3 philosophical approaches to research which are positivism, interpretive and postmodernism as seen on figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The three approaches to Qualitative research (Gephart, 2004)

This study will be using two questionnaires as the data collection method which focuses more on the interpretive approach. According to Gephart (2004:456-457) "The goal of interpretive research is to understand the actual production of meanings and concepts used by social actors

in real settings” this approach would be beneficial to this study as researching “the different meanings held by different persons or groups produce a sense of truth”(Gephart 2004: 457) as this responses given by the students and teachers will be subjective and based on their personal opinions and experiences this approach will help to understand “subjective opinions, experiences and feelings of individuals and thus the explicit goal of research is to explore the participants views of the situation being studied”(Dörnyei 2007: 38) The RQ of this study requires the views of Saudi students and their respective teachers so that a problem and possible solution to the Research questions of this study.

The questionnaire will focus on optional choices with the subjective questions focusing on a number scale type of question to judge the participants personal opinion. There will be two versions of the questionnaire so that both Saudi students and the teachers that are teaching them can share their opinions on the issue of the challenges of developing academic writing face by Saudi students studying in the UK.

Research method

The research methodology that will be employed will be based on two questionnaires which will be based on Qualitative responses. The first questionnaire (see appendix C) is for Saudi Students studying preparatory English courses in a private language academy in preparation for University and the second questionnaire (see appendix D) is for their respective teachers in the English Academy.

According to Richards, Ross and Seedhouse (2012: 10) A ‘research gap’ must be found in order to determine the scope of the research needed. As shown in my literature review there is a research gap on the difficulties of academic writing of Saudi students studying in the UK and both questionnaires are designed to identify and answer these gaps.

Participants

The participants of this questionnaire involved 10 students from Saudi Arabia who are studying at a private language academy in the UK and 4 teachers that are teaching Saudi students at this private language academy.

The criteria for participation in this study were that students must be Saudi nationals who have been educated in Saudi Arabia and are enrolled in an academic English preparation course in the UK. The teachers selected were teachers that have been teaching predominantly Saudi students since they started teaching at the academy. All participants were approached with a consent form to ensure the response rate was encouraging. For example various language academic were contacted in order to find the academy which had the most Saudi students present so that the data collection could have as many Saudi student responses as possible.

Knight and Pearson (2005) state that an affective collection method of participants is to use social media and advertising so the study messaged various language academies and Saudi UK student groups on social platforms such as Facebook and Twitter so that a good base of participants could be identified and contacted.

The questionnaire was designed with multiple choice questions with some questions having a numbered 1 to 10 responses so that a degree of feeling could be obtained which could illustrate

the answer in more detail for this study to understand the extent to which the respondent feels on any relevant issue (Dörnyei 2007)

Researchers role

I am an English Native teacher based in the UK I will be visiting the Preston English Academy based in Preston to conduct my study with the Saudi students and teachers teaching at this academy.

Student Questionnaire

The questionnaire has two sections Educational background and Academic writing so that the research questions can be fully addressed in the participants responses. There is a open ended question at the end of the questionnaire to get a more detailed open answer from participants as to how they feel they can improve their academic writing. At the end of the questionnaire applicants were invited to complete a more detailed open-ended section with just one student volunteering to complete a more detailed section of the questionnaire which had two questions pertaining to the difficulties of Academic writing and the main weakness or challenges of working on an Academic writing assignment.

There were 8 multiple choice questions and one open ended question. Participants were asked about their educational background in relation to Academic English as well as their current study at this school where they are undertaking a course to develop their Academic English writing skills. The questions also reflect on what aspects of Academic writing do they find challenging as well as how they feel they can improve their academic writing skills. A copy of the questionnaire is provided (see Appendix C)

The questionnaire was kept in a paper form with the students filling this in by hand so that it could be convenient and fast for the participants to respond to the questions in the questionnaire. Online surveys were not considered as there was a risk of getting a low response late from students as compared to asking them to sign a consent form and filling out a questionnaire in class. It is important to get the Saudi students input as the study is based on the challenges they face in developing Academic English writing in the UK.

Teacher Questionnaire

To ensure that the research is as objective as possible it would have to involve the teachers that interact and teach Saudi students on a day to day basis so that the teachers can share their opinion on what they feel is the challenges of developing Academic writing for Saudi students and what they feel could be done so that these challenges can be overcome.

The second questionnaire (see appendix D) is for their teachers in regards to their experience of teaching Saudi Arabian students in their Academic English development class. The questionnaire focuses on the teachers view point on the challenges and solutions to Academic writing based on their own experience of teaching Saudi students in class.

The questionnaire has 6 multiple choice questions with two open ended questions so that the teachers could respond to the research questions effectively. The questionnaire asked the teachers as to how long they have been teaching Academic English to Saudi students as the institute has been operational for the past 10 years teaching various big groups of Saudi students in the past. The teachers will be asked about the majority of Saudi students' motivational levels in class and challenges they face in developing Academic writing as well as the solutions they feel that could help in overcoming those challenges in two open ended questions designed to get a more insightful answer.

Procedure

To ensure the validity of both the questionnaires a pilot study was conducted with the target groups to ensure that the questionnaires are relevant and contain valid research topics without any errors. Dörnyei (2007) states "Just like theatre performances, a research study also needs a dress rehearsal to ensure the high quality (in terms of reliability and validity) of the outcomes in the specific context." (P.75) Therefore piloting is essential for this study so that this study remains reliable and valid. The proposed student questionnaire was given to two former Saudi Arabian students that used to study in the language academy and the proposed teacher questionnaire was given to 3 English teachers currently teaching Saudi students in another language academy. Important feedback with corrections were received and therefore both questionnaires were amended in line with the feedback received from the pilot phase.

The questionnaires and consent forms were handed out in the middle of an Academic writing class to both students and teachers at the language academy with all questionnaires being collected and the data being reported as valid. The data collected was then analysed with the results of the data being scrutinized and supported by the relevant literature with solutions being proposed.

Ethics

Ethics is an important aspect to any study conducted as the participants should consent to their data being shared to this study. A consent form was presented to each participant detailing what the study is for and how their data would be used. To maintain ethical approval Students and Teachers were given anonymity in the questionnaires to ensure their private data is protected. As students and teachers share the same classroom any opinion they share must be kept confidential and relevant to this study.

Limitations

The study could have been conducted better had there been more participants involved as there were just 4 teachers involved in the study alongside 10 Saud students. The method used was quite limited as none of the participants consented to being interviewed and this affected the quality of the results as a semi structured interview can produce more detailed insight into the date being collected and more systematic as compared to the questionnaire approach (Lynch, 1996).

Results

Introduction

In this chapter, the findings of the questionnaire will be reported both from the student's data and the teacher's data collected at the language academy.

Findings of the student questionnaire

In total 15 Saudi Arabian students are currently studying at the language academy where the questionnaire was conducted however 5 students declines to participate with just 10 students consenting to the questionnaire. The questionnaire was anonymous so therefore no data on the participants age or gender was collected so that the participants could share their opinion in confidence.

Student Participants length of study at the language academy

The statistical method of bar charts and pie charts were used for various responses so that the results could be displayed in an effective way as a collective result of the student responses.

The first question was designed to show the study that the students are all at different timelines of their development in academic writing as the language academy offers development courses for different periods of time. The results show that there is a mixture of timelines for students as five students have been studying at the academy between 7-12 months and 3 students who have studied two to six months.

A reason for most students studying for less than a year is that Saudi students arrive to study in the UK with a student visa and therefore the fact they stop studying after a year can be due to visa issues or the start of their respective courses at their future universities.

As seen on the results above most students have not undertaken any form of Academic English training before arriving to the UK which is a significant contribution to this study's finding as the study is aiming to recognise the root causes of the development of Academic writing difficulties for Saudi students in the UK with this result showing that 7 out of ten students did not receive any form of English training or tutoring before arriving to study in the United Kingdom. The finding does show that 2 students had General English training before arriving to the UK with just 1 student undertaking Academic English training.

From the 3 participants that responded to Question 2 that they had in fact received prior training the findings on Q3 show that this was relatively short term as 3 students responded with four

to seven months of training with a single student confirming they had studied for between 1-3 months.

The participants responded to this question of the ability of their English teacher in Saudi Arabia on a 1 to 10 scale with 1 being the weakest and 10 being the strongest. The participants response shows that the clear majority of 8 students had rated their previous English teacher as 3 or below which shows a big contrast to the 2 students that felt their previous teacher in Saudi Arabia had a high level of English.

Academic writing

Question 5 shows a mixture of responses from students based on their motivation level of learning Academic English writing with the majority of students falling below the 5-scale based on their motivational feeling with just 2 students feeling very motivated above the 5 mark.

The results here were expected due to the literature research pointing towards an issue with the lack of education in Academic English within the Saudi Arabian education system. Students responded as 4 students responded with a 1 on the scale of being very unprepared with just 2 students responding with a 9 as to being strongly prepared for Academic English which points towards an anomaly within the Saudi Arabian Education system with some students had good studies based on Academic English in their respective schools whilst others did not get the quality of study they feel they needed to be prepared.

1. Q7. Please can you rate between 1 to 4 on the most challenging parts of Academic writing with 1 being difficult and 4 being very easy.

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Referencing	4	2	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3
Critical thinking	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	1
Academic Writing grammar conventions	2	3	3	2	1	1	1	3	2	2

Adjusting to the differences between Arabic and English	3	4	2	3	3	3	3	2	4	4

All 10 participants were asked to use the number factor of 1 to 4 to assess the level of difficulty they found in the different aspects of academic writing with the respondents responding to 1 being the most difficult and 4 being the least difficult. 7 students responded with critical thinking being the most difficult aspect of academic writing and 3 students responding with Academic writing grammar conventions being the most difficult showing a mixture of responses. Referencing was seen as the least difficult aspect of Academic writing with 7 students responding to it with a 4 in the difficulty scale rating as being very easy. The results show that Critical thinking and Academic writing grammar conventions are the aspects which need to be focused on to help Saudi students improve their preparation for Academic writing.

Students responded to this question on how to tackle their Academic writing difficulties with the question giving them more than one possible solution to circle 7 students circled both extra classes on academic writing in Saudi Arabia before arriving to study in the UK and a recommendation to change the curriculum in Saudi Arabia to help with Academic English writing. 3 students circled other which would lead to a more detailed answer in Question 9.

Q9. If answered other in Question 8 please state what you think can be done to improve your skills in Academic English?

Three participants decided to give the other response which is stated as below without any corrections with transcription word for word:

Participant 1

I think it that I need more a help with teacher in class we some atimes struggle with understanding our Academy teacher accent he speak to fast and I feel shy to ask question because we aren't allowed to interrupt teacher in my last school in Saudi Arabia.

Analysis

The student feels there are issues with current studies in the UK at the academy where this student is studying academic English. The student states that they are having issues with understanding the lesson taught by the English teacher due to the speed of the speech. The student's response that they do not interrupt their current teacher due to the culture of study in Saudi Arabia where they aren't allowed to interrupt the teacher.

The student could possibly be advised that it is acceptable to raise your hands and ask questions mid lesson as per the study culture here which could possibly have be resolved with a cultural lesson given to new Saudi students that arrive to study in the UK to avoid this confusion. This also shows that many teachers may not be aware of Saudi students struggling in their classes due to a reluctance to communicate with the teacher.

Participant 2

I think if I had a assistant teacher who can also speak in Arabic to help me with problems in class I can study better.

Analysis

Student's brief answer points to the student feeling that they need a teaching assistant who can speak in Arabic that could aid them in their study.

Participant 3

My Highest school English grammar teacher in Saudi Arabia used to translate a lot of words for us in class which make it difficult for me to understand English. I am struggling to understand the English here in my academy. I have to use google translation to understand my teacher.

Analysis

This students response shows that this particular student is struggling with understanding English due to a previous teacher employing the Grammar Translation method to teach this student in school.

Teacher responses

The second questionnaire was directed at the 4 teachers in the Academy that are currently teaching Saudi students. The analysis below will focus on their responses. The questionnaire was anonymous so therefore no data on the participants age or gender was collected so that the participants could share their opinion in confidence.

As seen with the chart above the 4 teachers are relatively experienced with 2 teachers stating they have been teaching Saudi students between 3-5 years and 1 teacher confirming they had taught Saudi students at the academy between 5-10 years with just 1 teacher being relatively inexperienced with a response of 1 year or below.

All 4 participants stated that writing was the most challenging skill to teach Saudi students which shows an overwhelming response to this question with listening, speaking and reading not being a concern.

As seen above most teachers feel that the majority of Saudi students are very demotivated with 2 teachers responding with 1 on the scale and 1 teacher with 4 and 5 on the scale.

The above bar chart shows that the majority of teachers scored the level of engagement of the majority of Saudi students at below the 5-scale with it heading closer to it being disengaged with 2 teachers scoring it at 4 and each teacher responding with 2 and 3 on the scale.

Q5. On a scale of 1 to 10 how do the majority of Saudi students as a general perform on Academic writing assignments in class? (with 1 being very weak and 10 being very strong)

The teachers responded to the question of scale in terms of how well do the majority of Saudi students perform on Academic writing assignments with 2 teachers scoring it at the very weak end of the scale with a 1 on the scale and a teacher each scoring it at 2 and 4 on the scale showing that all the teachers on this survey feel that their Saudi students are performing relatively weak on academic writing assignments in class.

Q6. What type of Academic writing mistakes do you commonly see in the majority of your Saudi Students English writing work. Circle multiple if relevant.

The above question shows a breakdown of what the teachers feel are the aspects of Academic writing where they have seen the majority of their Saudi students make errors in. Academic grammar conventions and Critical thinking was the most popular choice as all 4 respondents circled this in their questionnaire. Cohesion in writing and Plagiarism was also a concern with 2 teachers selecting them in their answers. Coherence in writing was not seen as a common error with none of the teachers selecting it in their questionnaire.

Question 7

Why do you feel Saudi students struggle with Academic English writing?

Participant 1

Most of my students are from rich families and therefore lack motivation to study hard as they have been forced by their parents to attend this school with the exception of 1 or 2 students that are from poorer backgrounds and are working hard to improve.

Analysis

This participant believes the economic situation of the Saudi students have a correlation with their motivation in class and that the students are forced by their parents to study at the school in general with the exception of 1 or 2 students. The teacher feels the Saudi students from poorer backgrounds are generally more motivated.

Participant 2

There is a underlying problem with their previous teachers with the majority of my students showing surprise on the various Academic grammar conventions taught in the writing course as they have told me they have never practiced writing much in their previous schools in Saudi Arabia.

Analysis

This participant felt the majority of his Saudi students previous education experience was to blame with the teacher claiming their own Saudi students have also complained about not having previous lessons on Academic grammar conventions in their previous schools in Saudi Arabia.

Participant 3

Poor attendance and classroom behaviour. I feel most of my Saudi students do not participate and rarely attend which seems to show low motivation to learning Academic English especially with Academic writing where I have seen signs of plagiarism on some of the writing assignments I have set for my class.

Analysis

This participant feels that the majority of his Saudi students do not participate in class and have low motivation to learn Academic English with plagiarism being spotted by this teacher in some of their writing assignments.

Participant 4

With the exception of a few Saudi students I have taught in the past the vast majority show a lack of motivation to learn Academic English writing. I have taught various nationalities at this academy but the Saudi students rarely participate in class with poor attendance and preferring to sit amongst themselves instead of mixing in with other student nationalities.

Analysis

This participant feels there is low motivation from the majority of their Saudi students when it comes to learning Academic English writing. The participant also feels that the students don't participate in class and have poor attendance. The participant raises a new point for this study that Saudi students prefer to sit in their own social circles instead of socialising with other nationalities in the school.

Question 8

In your opinion how can Saudi Students improve their Academic English writing?

Participant 1

I feel the students should not be forced to study by their parents and should come of their own accord as the forceful nature of parents cause low motivation however the fact that students don't view this course seriously shows there may be a previous learning experience which has caused this possibly in Saudi Arabia.

Analysis

This participant feels that students should not be forced to attend by their parents and should have their own free will so that they are better motivated. The participant also feels that previous learning experiences in Saudi Arabia may have caused this low motivation.

Participant 2

The students that have studied with native teachers in private schools in Saudi Arabia show a higher level of ability compared to my students that have studied in Government schools in Saudi Arabia with non-native English teachers so I believe the education system must be reformed in Saudi Arabia to give these students a good chance of developing their academic writing skills from an earlier stage preferably with the English curriculum focusing more on writing.

Analysis

This participant shows a discrepancy between the students that studied with native English teachers in private school and non-native teachers in government schools with the private school students showing a higher level of English ability. This teacher also feels that the Saudi Arabian system should change the curriculum and have the English curriculum focusing more on writing to address this weakness.

Participant 3

Students should be given an Arabic and English-speaking teaching assistant when they first arrive here as I have noticed a lot of my Saudi students struggle to understand basic instructions in class and could do with a teaching assistant. I also feel their low level of attendance should be addressed as they are not attending class regularly in order to take benefit from the development of Academic English writing that takes place in our academy.

Analysis

This participant feels that students should be provided with an Arabic-English speaking teaching assistant in order to help the students settle in and understand basic instructions in class. The participant also feels that the low level of attendance should be addressed so that they can improve.

Participant 4

The Saudi students should participate more in class and avoid sitting among themselves in class so that they can free mix and use English a lot more instead of continuously communicating in Arabic. I also find that they can improve their Academic English writing abilities by having a curriculum in Saudi Arabia which places more importance on developing Academic writing skills with the vast majority of my students explaining to me they have never been taught this in school.

Analysis

This participant feels that there is a low level of participation due to Saudi students sitting amongst themselves and would like to see Saudi students mixing in more with other learners of English so that they avoid using their L1 which is Arabic. The participant also has been told by their students that they have never been taught Academic English writing skills in their previous schools in Saudi Arabia and recommends that the curriculum in Saudi Arabia should incorporate Academic writing skills.

Conclusion

This study has explored the various Research questions related to the Academic writing challenges of Saudi students. The next chapter will discuss the implications of this study.

Discussion

Introduction

This chapter will discuss the findings and the implications of this study. The limitations and strengths of this study will be discussed as well as recommendations that arise as a result.

The aim of this study is to identify challenges of developing Academic writing for Saudi ESL students in the UK. The literature review conducted could not identify any existing research done on Saudi ESL student's difficulties of developing Academic writing in the UK with the aim of this study is to fill the existing gap in research.

Research Implications

Issues discovered from the Student Questionnaire

Preparation for study in Academic English

The results from the questionnaire show that the majority of students in the study did not receive any previous Academic English training before arriving to the UK with the exception of 3 out of 10 students that had Academic English training before arriving to the UK. The lack of training by Saudi students prior to arriving to the UK is due to the lack of training courses available in Saudi Arabia due to a higher demand for General English courses. Most of the general public prefer to study general English so that they can understand Hollywood movies or travel to English speaking countries. In addition there is a shortage of Native English teachers that teach Academic English in Saudi Arabia. The finding that most of the students that received previous training had not had training lasting more than 7 months showing that it was a short term course which may not have properly prepared them in earnest for the rigours of Academic English writing in the UK.

Students in the study that undertook Academic English training before arriving to the UK do tend to perform better than students with no previous training. Due to a lack of previous Academic English training Saudi students struggle to understand basic concepts of Academic writing. The study also found that even when it comes to General English only 2 students out of 10 had any sort of previous General English training before arriving to the UK this as a result causes difficulties for Saudi students in Academic English classes in the UK as they cannot understand basic English instructions from their teachers and would therefore point towards a remedial measure to ensure that Saudi students understand basic instructions in class so that they can learn effectively.

Low motivation

Low motivation was expected to be a factor in this study however the fact that both the teachers and student findings resonate was an interesting find showing that this affecting classroom morale and student performance. Saudi Arabian students in the study responded that they were unmotivated to learn Academic English writing with 8 out of 10 students below the 5 scale out of 10 on how motivated they are in regards to learning Academic English writing however 2 students responded with very motivated with 1 student scoring a 7 and 1 student scoring a 9 on

the scale out of 10. This shows that not all students are demotivated. So that more students are motivated its important to address the reasons for their demotivation which can be due to the level of English of most students as the students without previous training in General English may struggle to understand basic classroom instructions or lesson content which in turn can raise the affective filter (Krashen 1987)

Lack of Academic English preparation in the Saudi Arabian education system

The results here were expected due to the literature research pointing towards an issue with the lack of education in Academic English within the Saudi Arabian education system. Students responded as 4 students responded with a 1 on the scale of being very unprepared with just 2 students responding with a 9 as to being strongly prepared for Academic English which points towards an anomaly within the Saudi Arabian Education system with some students had good studies based on Academic English in their respective schools whilst others did not get the quality of study they feel they needed to be prepared. This shows that there may be different standard levels of English classes in the vast country with some schools having better preparation classes than others which may need to be investigated further as to whether the Saudi education authorities should introduce curriculum changes to tackle this. The fact that this study could not investigate this further due to students declining to take an interview shows that there is not enough detail to pinpoint exactly what is the reason for Saudi students in this study feeling unprepared despite having studied a full English curriculum throughout school.

7 out of 10 students in the study feel that the curriculum in Saudi Arabia for English should be changed to have a focus on helping develop academic writing. This shows that Saudi students studying in the UK feel there is a void in the current curriculum which needs to be amended so that future Saudi students do not struggle with academic writing in the UK. 1 particular student referred to the Grammar translation method employed by their previous teacher in Saudi Arabia which that student blamed for their low level of English. This can be viewed in isolation as this was the only student to complain about this technique employed by their previous teacher as it could be just an isolated case with just the one teacher employing this technique and not the wider academic teaching community in Saudi Arabia. This can also be investigated further in a bigger sample size as to whether this has an effect on Academic writing skills on Saudi students studying in the UK.

Issues with Academic writing

7 out of 10 Saudi participants in the questionnaire felt that Critical thinking and Academic writing grammar conventions are the most challenging aspects of Academic writing this can again be linked with the second RQ which was set to investigate if the students L1 which is Arabic causes interference when acquiring the L2 English target language. The literature review found that there are a lot of grammatical differences between the Arabic language and the English language therefore this result was expected for example academic grammar convention requires writing in formal academic convention as well as writing in the third person etc. which is all foreign to the Arabic language. This therefore confirms that L1 interference plays an important role in the challenges faced in Academic writing by Saudi students in the UK.

The results show that Critical thinking and Academic writing grammar conventions are the aspects which need to be focused on to help Saudi students improve their preparation for

Academic writing as this is the area of academic writing Saudi students feel they struggle with the most. Students were also reluctant to conduct an interview to discuss this questionnaire in detail with no student volunteering to reveal their name or gender to the study with the preference to remain anonymous therefore future studies would be recommended to investigate this in further detail by finding volunteers that would be satisfied with having their gender and age revealed on the study so that a thorough investigation can be had to see if there is a difference in Academic writing challenges between male and female students or if age plays a factor in this. This study also has a limitation as no students agreed to be interviewed which could have produced more detailed data which could have been analysed.

This study would recommend further investigation as a more valid way of pinpointing these challenges by requesting student participants to produce an academic writing essay so that these errors could be investigated in further detail. Unfortunately, the students in this study refused to participate in regard to writing an academic essay therefore future studies would be recommended to investigate this in further detail.

Social factors

Students felt that they struggled with adjusting to study life in the UK which caused social anxieties that affects their learning experience. This was an expected finding as the literature review showed that many foreign students struggle with adjusting to social life in the UK as they feel homesick and go through a period of integration into a society which has a different language, culture and society as compared to the country they arrive from. Saudi students in this study also stated they would like help with adjusting to study life in the UK. This study would recommend that a cultural adjustment officer should be assigned to groups of Saudi students arriving to study so that they can help them with adjusting to social life as well as feeling comfortable in their new surroundings so that the integration phase is as fast and efficient as possible so that students can focus in class and learn Academic writing easily.

Classroom teacher difficulties in the UK

The Saudi students in this study felt that they could not understand their Academy's teacher's instructions in class due to the speed of speech and accent which may relate to why they are struggling with developing academic writing skills whilst studying in the UK. A possible explanation can be that due to a lack of previous training before arriving to the UK students have a low level of English listening comprehension skills which can cause difficulties in understand the teacher's speech in class. The study also found that these students were also reluctant to raise their hands and clarify their teacher's instructions in class which the student attributed to a study culture they experienced in Saudi Arabia where they felt they weren't allowed to interrupt the teacher in class. This point raised may need to be investigated further with a bigger sample size as this study is limited to a small sample of students with it being impossible to identify if this is a one off situation or a much wider phenomena in the Saudi education system.

A possible recommendation can be that students arriving to study in the UK be given introductory classes by bilingual Arabic and English teachers explaining classroom etiquettes and societal norms in student teacher interactions so that they are aware that it is okay to raise your hand and clarify teacher instructions. This can cause issues with the teachers in this study and in general with teachers throughout the UK if the students do not communicate what they are struggling with in class due to shyness or previous cultural norms in Saudi Arabia then the

teacher will not be able to identify and rectify what the students are struggling with in Academic English preparation classes.

Teachers can also be advised to speak slowly and much more clearly as the UK has many different accents which may confuse Saudi students who may have experienced just one particular form of English accent and therefore would need the teacher to talk more slowly and clearly so that all students can understand during class. Another recommendation would be to use CCQs (Concept checking questions) in class to ensure that students who are nodding yes to everything actually do understand what is being taught to them and not just shy or reluctant to clarify important points.

Bilingual teaching assistant (Arabic and English)

Students expressed need of a bilingual assistant teacher that is fluent in Arabic and English so that they can understand teacher instructions. This was prevalent with how the students produced detailed answers in the final question of the dissertation. This can be helpful for students with a low level of English as this is already employed in primary schools and high schools in the UK when a foreign student arrives to study so therefore this can be replicated in Academic English preparation courses in the UK so that new students can be helped in Preparatory Academic English classes in the UK. These assistant teachers can help explain different difficult concepts in class such as proof reading and paraphrasing etc. in a more understandable way in the students' L1 language so that they understand what the teacher is teaching them in class. This can also be quite a difficult solution as most Academies are running on small profit margins and employing a bilingual assistant teacher may be expensive. There is also an argument that when students are forced to learn in English and not rely on their L1 Arabic then they would acquire L2 faster so keeping a bilingual assistant teacher may be detrimental to their learning experience this study would recommend further studies to be conducted into the effects of Bilingual assistant teachers on Saudi students overcoming academic writing challenges in the UK.

Issues discovered from the Teacher Questionnaire

This study felt that it was important to include Teacher feedback as both sides of the spectrum must be analysed to ensure that the Saudi students and their Teachers can give their view points on the challenges of developing Academic English writing for Saudi students in the UK. The following issues were discovered from the 4 teachers that responded to this study's questionnaire.

Teacher experience

This was an important factor in this study as new teachers have different teaching perspectives compared to older more experienced teachers with this study showing that 3 out of 4 teachers in this study have been teaching Saudi students between 3 to 10 years in the UK therefore they will give more insight into the common challenges they see their Saudi students face on a year to year basis. This can also be detrimental to the study as the author of this study has also taught Saudi students in the past with past experiences potentially corrupting every teacher's subjective opinion on the matter which requires a fresh outlook on the situation. This can also be advantageous as a common trend does start to appear when a teacher teaches different Saudi students arriving from Saudi Arabia over a long period of time.

Writing is the most difficult skill to teach Saudi students

All 4 teachers in this study unanimously felt that writing is the most difficult skill to teach Saudi students. This shows that there is definite factors which are causing Saudi students to struggle with this essential skill in the English language which would contribute to Academic writing difficulties of Saudi students.

Possible reasons for this can be due to a lack of Writing practice in the Saudi English curriculum. The study would recommend further analysis and study to be done on whether the curriculum in Saudi Arabia is contributing to this or whether it's the student's L1 Arabic that contributes to student difficulties in writing in L2 English. The literature review in this study already points to the fact that Arabic and English writing are fundamentally different therefore this can be a difficult skill to acquire. This study is limited by the fact that there are just 4 teachers in this small sample size a more effective study would take a much larger sample size of teachers from different academies throughout the UK to get a more balanced outlook on this. Teachers also

Low motivation and engagement in class

The majority of teachers in this study felt that students weren't motivated or engaged in their classrooms. With all of the respondents rating motivation and engagement below the 5 scale out of 10. This relates well with the findings from the student questionnaire as students mentioned they did not understand teacher instructions and were too shy to approach their teachers for clarifications. This is reflected in the teacher responses as they feel their students don't participate in class and look demotivated and disengaged as any student studying in any class would be demotivated if they didn't understand their teacher. There is also another perspective on this as teachers stated that they felt there were factors contributing to this low motivation and engagement as the teacher respondent felt that economic factors contributed to a lack of motivation with rich parents forcing their students to study at this academy and students from lower economic backgrounds working harder than their rich counterparts. This study cannot verify if economic factors contribute to student motivation and engagement levels in class but a future study can investigate this further to ascertain if this is a contributory factor.

Poor classroom behaviour and attendance has also been attributed by a teacher within this study. This can be a contributory factor as to why Saudi students are struggling with developing Academic writing as attendance plays an important role in acquiring Academic writing skills if a student is not attending then they will definitely struggle with acquiring anything of note from classes. A recommendation could be that a behaviour officer is placed within this academy so that they can enforce attendance and find out why students are avoiding classes. This can also be linked to low motivation as the student finding shows that the majority of students are struggling to understand teacher instructions due to the teachers accent or speech speed or even low English comprehension skills therefore students may be displaying poor behaviour and low attendance as they feel they are not learning anything in class. This can be rectified if a bilingual teaching assistant is assigned to these students to ensure students understand what they are being taught, another preventative measure could be to ensure that more Academic English training courses are available in Saudi Arabia to help train these students before they arrive in the UK. This could be investigated further if future studies can interview Saudi students in the UK in a much wider sample size from various different academies as this situation may just be isolated to this academy alone.

One of the teacher respondents stated that they observed Saudi students sitting amongst themselves in class and not mixing in with other students which they felt affected their participation as the students would communicate with each other using their L1 instead of using English. This is consistent with the literature review as the review found that foreign learners find comfort in sitting with speakers of the same L1 due to social integration times as students are shy and nervous in their new surroundings. The study can recommend that this can be tackled efficiently by slowly weaning students off their own L1 learners by slowly integrating them into the class and mixing the class up to avoid these situations however it must be done slowly as to avoid raising the affective filter (Krashen 1987).

Aspects of Academic writing that Saudi students struggle with

The teacher respondents on the questionnaire felt that Academic grammar conventions and Critical thinking were the two main aspects their students struggle with in Academic writing which corresponds well with the Student responses as both students and teachers agree on the main aspects that are challenging for Saudi students. There may be a reason towards why Critical thinking is such a prevalent difficulty as the Saudi English curriculum may not develop critical thinking skills which is developed through previous Academic training experiences of Saudi students. This study is also limited to this response as a writing sample analysis could have given more insight as to what aspects of Critical thinking do Saudi students struggle with in their Academic writing essays.

Academic Grammar conventions being spotted by all the teachers in this study also confirm that students do indeed face this difficulty in this particular academy in the study therefore this points towards L1 interference taking place with students finding it difficult to come to terms to the English grammar conventions employed in Academic writing. This could also be rectified by extra training or classes in Saudi Arabia teaching students about Academic grammar conventions as well as a change in the Saudi English curriculum.

Plagiarism

2 teachers in this study felt plagiarism is a major factor where students are struggling to avoid direct or indirect plagiarism in their writing assignments. This could be due to previous learning experiences if their previous schools in Saudi Arabia did not teach them how to avoid plagiarising their work by mistake. This could also mean purposeful plagiarism as demotivated students are more likely to copy and paste answers or use easier means to complete their work if they are not motivated to develop their academic writing skills. Due to the ambiguous nature of this response an interview would have been more insightful in order to ascertain examples of plagiarism these teachers felt they saw in their Saudi students writing assignments as well as a study of Academic writing assignments produced by Saudi students in this academy unfortunately both students and teachers declined to take an interview which limits the findings of this study however future study can interview and acquire more insight into plagiarism present in Academic writing work produced by Saudi students in the UK.

Previous English teaching experience in Saudi Arabia

This study found that the Academy teachers had different view points as to what is contributing to the Academic writing difficulties of their own Saudi students. One of the respondents felt

that previous learning experiences in Saudi Arabia caused low motivation to study Academic English. There is a notion from one of the respondents that students that studied from native teachers in Saudi Arabia seem to perform better than students studying from non-native teachers. This is a new concept which needs further investigating as this was not in the literature review. There is a debate amongst the academic community as to the attributes of Native teachers compared to Non-native English teachers with some academics arguing that non native teachers can in some circumstances provide a better learning experience in terms of being a L2 learner themselves (Medgyes, 1992). This finding can provide a more detailed insight as to whether this affects Saudi learners in the same way it affects other learners. This advances current understanding that the Saudi English curriculum is to blame for current problems of Academic writing experienced by Saudi students and would require further study and analysis so that it can be studied further.

Limitations

There are a lot of limitations of this study which could have enhanced this study if it was implemented. The study was conducted at a small English academy in the city of Preston in England however this study could have been more comprehensive if it expanded its data collection size to include students and teachers from various geographical locations throughout the UK as this study shows conditions in this particular academy in Preston a much larger sample size comprising various Saudi students and teachers throughout the United Kingdom would have made the study more comprehensive and reliable.

The way the research was conducted could have included more qualitative methods such as Interviews for both Students and Teachers unfortunately this study did not gain consent from both groups for this study which could have given more detailed answers and valuable data to analyse. Future studies can include interviews to give more detailed insights into challenges of developing academic writing for Saudi students in the UK.

The Academic writing genre can be best analysed by analysing student academic writing (Hyland 2004). This study could not analyse student writing as the students declined to take part in an academic writing essay which could be analysed. A further study to analyse student Academic writing would deliver more in depth findings as to what parts of academic writing Saudi students find challenging. Another RQ was based on whether L1 interference contributes to academic writing difficulties of Saudi students. The findings from the questionnaires do help towards attributing L1 interference as a possible factor however an in-depth analysis of students Academic writing in Arabic and English could help the study identify such issues in more detail.

Both questionnaires were kept anonymous due to the reluctance of the participants to reveal their gender or age so that their identity could not be deciphered as they wanted to reveal their true feelings about their own current and previous teachers as well as the challenges they face with academic writing. Students were therefore more complicit in their assessment as they felt safe with anonymity however this study would recommend a future study which would take gender and age into account so that the differences between Saudi Male and Female students can be noted as different genders or age groups may experience different challenges of developing academic writing.

Even though the Questionnaires were piloted and designed to elicit true responses from participants things can go wrong in the data collection process. Some participants may have

taken the study seriously whilst others may have been reluctant to express their true feelings due to the nature of the study. Teachers and students in this academy may be mindful of what they say about their fellow students and teachers and therefore many responses may have been omitted which could have benefitted this study. There is also the Hawthorne effect (Adair and John 1984) wherein students and teachers may have an observer bias when it comes to research therefore can be unreliable as students or teachers may alter their responses. An ideal study would observe an Academic English writing lesson in a naturalistic setting without the student and teachers knowing that they are being observed however this would bring up ethical issues where it is unethical to observe a classroom in this way without consent.

Credibility is an important element of any study and this study has limitations when it comes to credibility as the results must reflect the reality and subjective views of the Academic writing challenges faced by Saudi students studying in the UK. This study would have been more credible had it been conducted with a bigger pilot size of Saudi students scattered across the United Kingdom.

The dependability of this study relied on the methodical process of qualitative research which can easily be repeatable by other studies however the omission of interviews can dent this dependability as a true qualitative research would have taken interviews into consideration.

The confirmability of this study has been compromised as personal biases are apparent between students and teachers of this study. Different students and teachers have different biases based on their previous experiences as shown in the different aspects of the results. How can the study ascertain if a certain student's isolated bad experience with a previous teacher doesn't affect their response to this study? Or a teacher's previous experience with a rogue student who just didn't care about learning affect their understanding of academic writing difficulties of Saudi students? It would be difficult to find out therefore the study is limited to the extent that all responses have an element of bias as does any study which conducts subjective research. This study tried to tackle this bias by asking general questions which relate to the majority of Saudi students and not selective.

The transferability of this research can be transferred to other settings as this study was based on an English Academy based in the United Kingdom. However, the responses and findings may differ between different academies throughout the UK as different academies have different teaching styles and facilities therefore this study is limited to this academy's own unique settings and teaching staff. Students from different regions of Saudi Arabia may have different learning experiences as students from urban backgrounds may have had a different education experience compared to students from rural backgrounds. To tackle these future studies can use a more quantitative approach to research to ascertain certain backgrounds of students so that data can be analysed in a more effective way.

Future research

The findings of this study have been very helpful as it has highlighted many different aspects of why Saudi students struggle to develop academic writing in the UK. This study has found that various factors work in combination to cause challenges in developing academic writing with many key facets contributing to this such as previous learning experiences, social integration, current UK classroom environment, teacher input and L1 interference contributing to this difficulty. This study also found that academic writing challenges can be overcome with extra academic English classes taking place before students arrive to the UK as well as the

introduction of a bilingual teaching assistant to help students learn better in class and overcome the language barrier.

New lines of enquiry has been created as a result of these findings as further study and research is needed to investigate the previous learning experiences of Saudi students in Saudi Arabia as both students and teachers in this study point towards an issue with the English curriculum and teaching practices in Saudi Arabia therefore research on what exactly is wrong and needs correcting in the Saudi English curriculum and teaching practice would help to identify and recommend possible remedies to help future Saudi students arrive to the UK prepared to easily learn how to write Academic English.

This research design is adequate in terms of qualitative research however future research designs should include interviews so that a more detailed insight is acquired. Future studies should also analyse student academic writing so that a more detailed analysis of academic writing can be conducted. However, this research raises further questions as to how exactly does the Arabic language contribute to Academic English writing difficulties? How does the current learning environment contribute to academic writing difficulties? How does a particular teaching methodology such as the grammar translation method contribute towards academic writing difficulties? These are all valid questions which could contribute to a more holistic answer to the issue at hand.

Conclusion

There is hope and aspirations that this study has contributed to the academic community in regard to being able to comprehend the challenges of developing academic writing for Saudi Arabian ESL students in the UK. This was an important study as many thousands of Saudi students struggle with this crucial skill of Academic writing in UK education institutions every year with many students failing to pass their course due to this deficiency. This therefore necessitated a study which could identify what these challenges are and whether the students L1 Arabic contributed to this weakness as well as a remedial recommendation as to how students can be helped to face these challenges.

At the beginning of this study the main objective of this study was to ascertain Challenges of developing Academic writing for Saudi ESL students in the UK. This study comprised of three important research questions which were as follows:

1. What challenges, in terms of developing academic writing, do Saudi students face whilst studying in the UK?
2. Does L1 interference contribute to academic writing difficulties for Saudi students?
3. How can Saudi students be helped to face the challenges of academic writing?

This study therefore set out to conduct an existing literature research to ascertain what the academic community had discovered in regards to these important RQs to this study. A lot of valuable research data was discovered as a result and contributed to this study's literature review. This helped the study to identify the gaps in the research as there was no data available on the current situation of Saudi students studying in the UK to develop academic writing therefore the qualitative research conducted in a UK language academy was ground breaking as no study had yet to observe this situation in regard to this RQs of this study. This study managed to pinpoint many valuable aspects which went towards answering the RQs of this study however there were some limitations as the quality of the research could have been improved had there been a detailed interview or bigger research data comprising Saudi students and teachers from across the UK.

This study therefore opened up future potential research into the challenges faced by Saudi students within UK universities. It would be interesting to compare the challenges faced by Saudi students in UK English academies and UK universities as to analyse how the different learning environment and teaching methodology can affect academic writing development. With a better understanding of what these challenges are educators and academic in this field can help future generations of Saudi students studying in the UK. Overall this study would judge itself to be successful if it could contribute to this solution as the main aim of any educator is to ensure that students from all backgrounds have the same chance of success and this alone remains the overall goal of this study to ensure future Saudi students are successful in their academic pursuit abroad.

Acronyms

EFL= English as a Foreign Language

ESL= English as a Second Language

NES= Native English Students

NNES= Non Native English Students

NS= Native Students

TEFL= Teaching English as a Foreign Language

TESOL= Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages

UK= United Kingdom

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Appendix A

Participant guidance sheet

29/07/2017

Dear Participants,

My name is Umair Siddiqui and I am working on a Masters in TESOL with Applied Linguistics dissertation project on the Academic writing difficulties of Saudi Arabian students studying in higher education in the United Kingdom.

I would like to thank you for volunteering to take part in my study and would like to emphasize that this study is completely anonymous and does not require your name so that you can share your thoughts and feelings in confidence.

The main aim of this study is for the academic community to learn more about the difficulties that Saudi students face in academic writing whilst studying in the UK. The goal is to ensure that the main problems can be identified and that by the end of this study recommendations can be made to the academic community and educational institutions to help support current and future Saudi students in the UK with developing their academic writing.

If you have any concerns or feedback regarding this study you are welcome to contact me or my supervisor as below:

Researcher: Umair Siddiqui Email: unsiddiqui1@uclan.ac.uk

Supervisor: Karen Fiona Smith Email: KFSmith@uclan.ac.uk

Study participation consent form

Study: Academic writing difficulties of Saudi students studying in the UK

Project Researcher: Umair Siddiqui

Project Supervisor: Karen Smith

- I have read through the guidance information sheet provided by the researcher and have read and understood the information regarding this study.
- I have been given the opportunity to ask the researcher questions and have them answered.
- I understand and give consent for the answers I provide in the survey to be used for this study.
- I understand and consent to my anonymous participation in this study.
- I understand that participation is voluntary and I can withdraw my participation at any time from this study and can decline to answer any question.
- If I withdraw from this study I understand that all my data collected will be destroyed and will not be used in this study.
- I agree to participate in this study.

Participant signature: _____

Date: _____

Participant name: _____

Appendix C

Student Questionnaire

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. This survey is dedicated to establishing how you feel about academic writing in your current study here in the UK and about your past learning experiences. This questionnaire is part of my dissertation that I am doing for my MA in TESOL with applied linguistics at the University of Central Lancashire.

This questionnaire is completely anonymous and there are no right or wrong answers. Please share your personal opinions as transparently as you can so that it can help this study's findings.

Thank you for your time and participation.

I consent to my participation in this study

Please select the correct answers below:

Educational background

(Please circle one response only.)

2. How long have you been studying at this school?

1 month

2-6 months

7-12 months

13 months or more

Q2. Have you received any of the following previous training in Saudi Arabia before arriving to the UK? (Please circle 1 or more if appropriate)

Academic English

General English

None

3. If you answered yes to Question 2, How long have you received training for ?

(1-3 months)

(4-7 months)

(8 months – 1 year)

(2 – 4 years)

(5 years or more)

4. On a scale of 1 to 10 in Saudi Arabia how would you rate the level of English of your English teacher in school?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Academic writing

5. On a scale of 1 to 10 how motivated are you to learn academic English writing? (1 being very unmotivated and 10 being very motivated)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

6. On a scale of 1 to 10 how do you feel your studies of English in the Saudi education system prepared you for Academic English writing? (1 being very unprepared and 10 being strongly prepared)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

7. Please can you rate between 1 to 4 on the most challenging parts of Academic writing with 1 being Easy and 4 being the most difficult.

Referencing _____

Critical thinking in writing _____

Academic writing grammar conventions _____

Adjusting to the differences in Grammar conventions between Arabic and English _____

8. What do you think can be done to help improve your skills in Academic English writing ? (You can circle one or more as appropriate)

-Help with adjusting to study life in the UK (social integration)

-Extra classes on Academic writing in Saudi Arabia before arriving to study in the UK

-Change of curriculum in Saudi Arabia to help with Academic English writing.

-Other (please go to Question 9)

9. If answered other in Question 8 please state what you think can be done to improve your skills in Academic English?

Appendix D

Teacher Questionnaire

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. This survey is dedicated to establishing how you feel about teaching academic writing to your Saudi students in class. As a teacher you will have personal views on the strengths and weaknesses of your students as a result your responses on this anonymous questionnaire will help to answer the studies question as to why Saudi students struggle with academic English writing and how the study can recommend any solutions to help them.

This questionnaire is completely anonymous and there are no right or wrong answers. Please share your personal opinions as transparently as you can so that it can help this study's findings.

A

Thank you for your time and participation.

I consent to my participation in this study

Please select the correct answers below:

1. How long have you been teaching Academic English?
1 year or below 2-3 years 3-5 years 5-10 years 10 years or above
2. Which skill would you say is the most challenging to teach Saudi students in general?
Writing Listening Speaking Reading
3. On a scale of 1 to 10 How would you rate the level of motivation of your Saudi students in class.
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
4. On a scale of 1 to 10 how engaged are your Saudi students to the lesson in terms of participating and asking questions?
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

5. On a scale of 1 to 10 how do Saudi students as a general perform on writing assignments in class?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

6. What type of Academic writing mistakes do you commonly see in your Saudi Students English writing work. Circle multiple if relevant.

Academic Grammar conventions Cohesion Paraphrasing

Coherence in writing Researching relevant topics and references

Critical thinking Plagiarism

7. Why do you feel Saudi students struggle with Academic English writing?

8. In your opinion how can their Academic English writing be improved?
